

National Recycling Network for the collection, recovery and recycling of wooden waste streams

An Italian national consortium works on enhancing objectives concerning post-consumer wood packaging like palettes, boxes, crates, cages and reels for cables. The consortium is also involved in managing the recycling process for all wooden scraps such as industrial waste (panels cuttings, etc.) and urban waste (e.g. dismissed furniture). The recycling scheme implemented allows to recover also other typologies of materials, such as plastics, metals, paper, etc. After collection and before mechanical treatment there is a separation process of different materials. The collection is carried out by common municipal collection as well as by private operators. The consortium works on non-profit base and is part of a national packaging consortium. All activities are contributing to objectives of national interest, in "guaranteeing sustainable production and consumption models".

Image: Rilegno

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Production waste is prevented, and the performance of the packaging is optimized by extended and improved use of packaging in the cascading use
- ▶ Collecting waste from public, industrial and commercial sites as raw material for new products is upcycling
- ▶ Legal basis for wood packaging recycling is given
- ▶ Public and market acceptance of waste wood reuse is enhanced through the activities of the consortia
- ▶ Recovery, extracting raw material from the collected volumes is innovative technology
- ▶ Recycling and reuse, promotes the economy of products obtained from the recycling of wood.

Regional coverage and transferability

The national consortium for wooden packaging came to existence in Southern Europe, where there is a lot production of heavy machinery and basically not much fresh wood. Machines are often packed into wooden packaging, which then also takes space to store. Therefore, the network might regionally-wise fit into many countries that have other post-consumer waste streams such as furniture. Also, different kind of municipals waste streams can be collected. However, higher barriers exist in the regions, that has the governance at a very regional level and for the waste streams no centralized systems are available.

